

ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VALVE-REGULATED LEAD-ACID BATTERIES AFTER EXPIRY OF HALF OF THE NOMINAL SERVICE LIFE

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Abstract: Results were presented on examinations of two valve-regulated lead-acid (VRLA) batteries AGM SVT 300 after six-year exploitation in two industrial systems of uninterruptible power supply. Batteries of the same type, with the nominal service life of twelve years, operated with similar load and the number of cells, but in various temperature conditions. Battery B1, operating without a proper air-conditioning for a long time, expressed failure of three battery cells (out of total 106). These failures were followed by significant characteristic degradation of another four cells after completion of the charging process of the previously deeply discharged battery. In the case of the battery B2, exploited with good air-conditioning, characteristics of the 100 battery cells (out of total 102) were spotless during the discharge of the 80% of nominal capacity, as well as during the following charging. From two cells from the battery circuit, not being from the same batch as the remaining hundred cells, was discharged only 30% of the nominal capacity. Voltage variations of the weak battery cells were analyzed, as well as their failure mechanisms. Implemented procedure for equalization of the VRLA battery's cells after accomplishing charging process was described. A practice of batteries operation with rectifiers that would enable their operation during the entire declared service life was proposed.

Key words: *valve-regulated lead-acid battery, discharging, charging, ambient temperature, battery cell voltage*

АНАЛИЗА ЕЛЕКТРИЧНИХ КАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ХЕРМЕТИЗОВАНИХ ОЛОВНИХ БАТЕРИЈА AGM SVT 300 НАКОН ИСТЕКА ПОЛОВИНЕ НОМИНАЛНОГ ЖИВОТНОГ ВЕКА

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Кратак садржај: Представљени су резултати испитивања две херметизоване оловне батерије типа AGM SVT 300 након шестогодишње експлоатације у два индустријска система непрекидног напајања. Батерије истог типа, номиналног животног века дванаест година, радиле су са сличним потрошачима и бројем ћелија, али у различитим температурним условима. Код батерије B1, која је дуго радила без одговарајуће климатизације дошло је до отказа три ћелије (од укупно 106). Ови откази су праћени значајном деградацијом карактеристика још четири ћелије након завршетка процеса пуњења претходно дубоко испражњене батерије. Код батерије B2, експлоатисане са добром климатизацијом, карактеристике 100 ћелија батерије (од укупно 102) биле су беспрекорне и приликом прањења 80% номиналног капацитета, и након накнадног пуњења. Из две ћелије у ланцу, које нису припадале истој производној серији као осталих сто, испражњено је само 30% номиналног капацитета. Анализиране су одступања напона слабих ћелија обе батерије, као и механизми њиховог отказа. Описан је примењени поступак за уједначавање напона ћелија херметизованих оловних батерија након завршетка процеса пуњења. Предложени су

поступци рада батерија са исправљачима који би омогућили њихову експлоатацију током комплетног декларисаног животног века.

Кључне речи: *херметизована оловна батерија, пражњење, пуњење, температура амбијента, напон ћелије батерије*

1. INTRODUCTION

Contemporary power plants and industrial facilities, most often built several decades ago, operate in a different business environment than in a time when they were put into operation. Neoliberal trends in the industrial management points accent on the maximum technological process automation, as well as the significant reduction of the production costs. This approach led to the great reduction of the employee's number, particularly in the maintenance and production branches. In such conditions, when the industrial facility has to operate with the minimum engagement of the few engineers, technicians and workers in the maintenance department for the electric equipment, selection of the maintenance-free devices becomes the imperative. Such a case is also with the storage batteries, representing the bases of the uninterruptible power supply systems in power plants and industrial facilities. On occasions when it is not possible to provide the special rooms for the accommodation of the vented lead-acid batteries, with special systems for ventilation and fire protection, as well as the impracticable daily practice of the electrolyte's characteristic inspection, procurement of the valve-regulated lead-acid (VRLA) batteries may be the optimal solution. Valve-regulated lead-acid batteries are often called "maintenance-free batteries". It is partially correct, since the adding of water or the electrolyte gravity measurement does not have to be performed. Yet, occasional examinations and the battery cycling are necessary.

On the other hand, valve-regulated lead-acid batteries are very sensitive to the ambient temperature, imposing the main maintenance task to be the ambient temperature regulation below the limit value of 25°C, regardless of the period of day or year. It is clear that this request demands installation of the proper air-conditioning in the room where the battery is situated. Operation with the ambient temperature increased for every 8°C above the limit of 25°C causes the battery service life to halve [1]. Yet, battery operation with a high ambient temperature may be very dangerous, particularly during the recharging of the previously discharged battery, as well as in other situations when high current flows through the battery circuit. In such cases may occur breach of the battery circuit, i.e., much earlier battery cell failure than expected by the mere monitoring of the ambient temperature.

In the paper were presented results recorded following the six-year exploitation of the valve-regulated lead-acid batteries of type AGM SVT 300 in one industrial facility in Serbia.

2. CHARACTERISTICS OF VALVE-REGULATED LEAD-ACID BATTERIES AGM SVT 300

For installation in two direct-current distribution systems of one industrial facility were selected 300 ampere-hour (Ah) valve-regulated lead-acid (VRLA) batteries of type AGM SVT 300, made by the "Sunlight" company [2]. Valve-regulated lead-acid batteries of AGM (*Advanced Glass Mat*) series use the compressed absorption separator made of glass microfibers to minimize self discharge and the loss of active material [2]. Batteries of AGM series do not utilize the boost charge mode, so the battery cell voltage is always maintained in the range 2.25 – 2.3 V. Therefore, rectifier designed for operation with the AGM series VRLA batteries may be simplified, that is, without the charging mode switch. Rectifier may operate only in a float charge mode, with no need for implementation of the boost charge and equalizing charge, as well as without the automatic operation mode [2]. Proper operation of the AGM SVT batteries is independent of position [2]. An important benefit that these batteries give is the possibility of high-current charging, with a maximum charging current up to

$2.5 \cdot I_{C10}$ (I_{C10} – ten-hours discharge current; $2.5 \cdot I_{C10} = 75$ A for 300 Ah battery). In this way the charging process of the discharged battery is significantly accelerated, enabling the battery to operate with rectifiers of much higher power than usual. Nominal service life of the AGM SVT batteries is 12 years, for the ambient temperatures up to 25°C, or 15 years for the ambient temperatures up to 20°C. Beside the specified limitations, the manufacturer specifies that batteries of AGM SVT series may operate in the wide ambient temperature range from -15°C up to +45°C [2] (naturally, with great influence on the battery service life limitations and available battery capacity [1]).

3. PROCEDURE FOR THE BATTERIES EXAMINATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE PROCURED RESULTS

Two batteries “Sunlight” AGM SVT 300 were examined during the year cycling and, hence, during the charging process of the previously deeply discharged batteries. During the discharging, as well as during the battery charging, voltages on all battery cells were measured every hour. The total voltage at battery terminals was also measured, as well as the battery current (both during charging and discharging). Battery cell voltage was measured by the instrument “Fluke” 289, with a declared uncertainty of measurement being 0.025% during the measurement of direct voltage, for the voltage range up to 5 V [3].

Storage batteries with the nominal capacity of 300 Ah were discharged by the ten-hour-discharge current (30 A). Batteries were discharged as long as the 80% of the nominal capacity was released. If the voltage of individual cells fell below the threshold of 1.8 V, discharging process was stopped, with the weak cells being excluded from the battery circuit. Weak cells were later returned to the battery circuit prior to the beginning of the charging process.

At the beginning of the charging process, the maximum battery current was defined by the rectifier of the nominal output parameters 220 V, 63 A. Seeing the direct current consumers could not be disconnected during the cycling and examination of batteries, rectifier’s maximum output current was additionally decreased by 3 – 5 A. Therefore, the initial current of the battery charging was in the range 58 – 60 A. Rectifier’s operation in the current regulation mode did not last long (between one and two hours), being followed by the significant drop of the battery current. Several days after the completion of the battery charging process was performed another procurement of all the battery cell data.

During the results analysis were used mean values of the battery cell voltage, as well as the variations of the minimum and maximum battery cell voltages from the average values of obtained results.

4. EXAMINATION RESULTS OF THE ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BATTERIES AGM SVT 300 AND DISCUSSION

Following the expiry of the half of nominal service life of two batteries AGM SVT 300 in the industrial facility, a cycling process on both batteries was performed. This was the first cycling process implementing deep discharging of batteries installed six and a half years ago (battery B1, 106 cells) and five and a half years ago (battery B2, 102 cells), respectively. Deep discharge of the 80% of the nominal capacity was necessary in order to establish the batteries' serviceability, as well as to estimate possibility of the further exploitation of the batteries AGM SVT 300.

Due to malfunction of the air-conditioning system installed in the battery room, battery discharging was, as well as the latter battery charging, performed on a relative high temperature of 30°C. Prior to the battery B1 discharging was assumed that the cell no. 4 was in a bad condition (cell voltage being 1.8 V, in comparison with 2.25 V on the nearby cells). The hypothesis was immediately confirmed, since as long as the rectifier was turned off, battery cell voltage quickly fell down to 0 V. Therefore battery B1 cell no. 4 was immediately disconnected from the battery circuit and shorted, and the discharging process of the remaining 105 cells started. After the eight hours of

discharging using the ten-hour-discharge current (30 A for a 300 Ah battery), planned 80% of the nominal capacity (C_{nom}) was discharged. Yet, not all the cells in the battery circuit could provide such amount of energy. From the cell no. 98 was discharged 50% of the nominal capacity, while from the cell no. 93 was depleted 67% C_{nom} . When voltage of these weak cells fell down to 1.8 V, cells no. 93 and 98 were also disconnected from the battery circuit and shorted. Following the completion of the discharging process, cells no. 93 and 98 were returned to the battery circuit.

Figure 1. Average battery cell voltages during the discharging process of battery B1

In the Fig. 1 was presented change of the average cell voltage of the battery B1 as a function of the discharge duration. Battery B1 was discharged 8 hours, using the average discharge current of 30.1 A. From the Fig. 2 may be seen large variations of the extreme values of the battery cell voltages from the average battery B1 cell voltage, particularly during the first five hours of the discharge process. Cause of the specified variations (up to -9% , right y-scale in the Fig. 2) is the much faster voltage decline on the cells no. 98 (excluded from the battery B1 circuit after five hours of discharge) and no. 93 (shorted after six and a half hours of discharge). Fig. 2 is a good illustration on a negative influence of the two mentioned weak cells on a state of storage battery B1. A relative variation of the minimum cell voltage in the battery B1 from the average value was recorded after the five hours of discharging, in order to decline to only 2.5% after the eight hours discharging. The reason is exclusion of the cells no. 93 and 98 from the battery circuit. Data on voltage of the weakest cell in the battery circuit is very important, since the voltage of the weakest cell determines the battery autonomy. When voltage of one cell of the battery AGM SVT 300 declines below the threshold of 1.8 V, discharge of the complete battery circuit have to be terminated.

As it was earlier noticed, battery B1 protractedly operated without a proper air-conditioning, thus exposed to the unacceptably high ambient temperature. That was not the case with the battery B2, always operating with functional air-conditioning and, therefore, with appropriate ambient temperature up to 25°C . Although the same type, same manufacturer and similar service life, characteristics of the battery B2 were substantially different in comparison with battery B1.

In the Fig. 3 was presented change of the average cell voltage of the battery B2 as a function of the discharge duration. Discharge process, as in the case of battery B1, lasted for eight hours, using the ten-hour-discharge current. Yet, the average battery B2 discharge current was slightly higher, being 31.3 A. This is why the average battery B2 cell voltage was slightly lower in comparison with the battery B1 (compare data from the Figs. 1 and 3).

Whence the battery B2 (with 102 cells AGM SVT 300) was discharged by the ten-hour-discharge current, two weak cells were identified (no. 81 and 84). Voltage of these cells has fallen on threshold 1.8 V already after discharging of 30% of the nominal capacity (nearly 90 Ah). Whence detailed inspection of these cells was performed, it was noticed that two weak cells do not

belong to the same batch as the other hundred cells in the battery circuit. Although the cells no. 81 and 84 were new made in the moment of installation and could not be much older from the other cells in the circuit, nevertheless it appeared that unwelcome practice of mixing the storage battery cells from the various production series significantly weakens the battery circuit. Even in the presented case, when only two cells from the different batch were added, battery circuit capacity was reduced down to just a third of the storage battery's nominal capacity.

Figure 2. Variations of minimum and maximum values of the battery cell voltages from the average battery cell voltage during the discharging process of the battery B1

Several implemented cycling processes during the six-year exploitation would certainly diminish difference between the cells from different batches, leading to the equalization of their characteristics (anyhow, during the six-year exploitation of the battery B2 were several occasions when battery discharged for several hours due to various causes that initiated the rectifier failure). Yet, it appeared that from the absorbed-electrolyte VRLA batteries may be successfully discharged 80% of nominal capacity after nearly six-year exploitation (that is, the half of the nominal service life) even in the case that there was no periodic cycling. Nevertheless, to achieve this possibility, necessary conditions were that all the cells in the battery circuit were from the same batch, as well as the battery cells temperature did not exceed permitted 25°C.

Figure 3. Average battery cell voltages during the discharging process of battery B2

Also in the case of battery B2 were, during the primary three hours of charging, recorded very large absolute and relative variations of the measured battery cell voltages, primarily regarding variations of minimum voltages in comparison with the average battery cell voltages (over 12%; Fig. 4). Such large variations were affected by the battery cells no. 81 and 84. These cells expressed very sharp voltage decline, so the cell voltages fell down to 1.8 V already after the three-hour discharge and depleted 30% of the nominal capacity. Immediately after the exclusion of the critical cells, minimum relative voltage variation of the battery B2 cells declined down to only 1%, in order to increase the relative voltage variation of the weakest battery cell from the average cell voltage at the end of the discharge process up to 5%. At the end of the eight-hour discharge, relative voltage variations of the extreme cell voltage values, in comparison with average cell voltages, were between -5% and $+2\%$ (Fig. 4). Due to discharge of the slightly higher capacity of battery B2, in comparison with battery B1, battery B1 expressed slightly lower variations of the battery cell voltages, being between -3% and $+1.5\%$ (Fig. 2). Specified variations of the battery cell voltages, following the discharge of high battery capacity, represent the basis for recommendations that lead-acid batteries, and particularly valve-regulated ones, must not be discharged above the depletion of 80% of the nominal capacity [1, 4].

Figure 4. Variations of minimum and maximum values of the battery cell voltages from the average battery cell voltage during the discharging process of the battery B2

In Fig. 5 was presented an average increase of the battery B1 cell voltage during the charging process. Due to malfunction of the air-conditioning in the room of battery B1, charging, as well as discharging process, was accomplished on relatively high temperature of nearly 30°C . The battery B1 charging process began in current regulation mode, *i.e.*, having constant charge current of 58 A (another 5 A flown to the consumers). Already after one hour battery current has fallen down to 44 A, further decreasing down to 11 A after eight hours of charging.

In Fig. 6 were presented both absolute and relative variations of the recorded extreme values of the battery cell voltages from the average values. Increase of the relative variations of the maximum cell voltage of the battery B1 during the primary hours of the charging process was affected by the great voltage rise on the battery cell no. 98. Although a significant capacity was depleted from the cell no. 98 ($50\% C_{\text{nom}}$), expecting its partial recovery after the battery B1 cycling, the voltage of this cell started to rise much faster than in other cells, reaching 2.82 V after two hours and nearly 90 Ah of the recovered storage battery capacity (nearly 30% of the nominal value, following the discharge of $80\% C_{\text{nom}}$). After three hours, charging of the battery B2 was briefly interrupted, having cell no. 98 shorted and permanently excluded from the battery circuit. Influence of the cell no. 98 may be most explicitly seen from the data presented in Fig. 6, by comparison of variations of the maximum battery cell voltage after three and four hours of the battery B1 charging.

Until the end of the charging there were no additional cell exclusion, but the voltage on even four cells (no. 33, 73, 74 and 93) rose above 2.6 V! On remaining hundred cells, battery voltage remained in the acceptable voltage of 2.25 – 2.3 V.

Figure 5. Average battery cell voltages during the charging process of battery B1

During the control performed the next day on the battery B1, after the completion of the charging process, on battery cell no. 74 was measured voltage of 5.1 V. For a lead-acid battery cell, with the usual floating voltage being in the range of 2.23 – 2.25 V this was unexpectedly high value! The surprise was much greater since the previous day from this battery cell was discharged 80% of the nominal battery capacity, without any problem. Due to the quick voltage drop on the battery cell no. 74 after the rectifier was turned off, caused by the minor load current of nearly 3 A, also the cell no. 74 had to be shorted and the battery B1 circuit was reduced down to 103 cells.

Figure 6. Variations of minimum and maximum values of the battery cell voltages from the average battery cell voltage during the charging process of the battery B1

Battery cell voltages of all the remaining 103 cells of the battery B1 were measured three days after the completion of the charging process. Significant voltage decrease on the critical four cells was spotted (Fig. 6). On the other hand, high voltage (2.47 V) appeared on the battery cell no. 12, having good characteristics during both discharging and charging processes. The failure of several battery cells and high voltage of many remaining cells finally led to the conclusion that battery B1 have to be replaced, beside the expiry of only half of the nominal service life.

In the Fig. 7 was presented an average increase of the battery B2 cell voltage during the charging process, while in the Fig. 8 were shown both absolute and relative variations of the recorded minimum and maximum cell voltages from the average values of the battery B2 cell voltages. Data presented in the Fig. 8 are particularly interesting, since during the charging process all the 102 cells were in the battery B2 circuit, including the weak cells no. 81 and 84. None of the battery B2 cells were excluded from the battery circuit during the charging process. Data on the battery cell voltage variations point on the characteristics of the two weak cells of the valve-regulated lead-acid battery AGM SVT 300 during the charging process of the previously discharged battery.

Immediately before the start of the charging process, the critical cells voltage (no. 81 and 84) was approximately 0.17 V higher (nearly 8%) than the other cells voltage (Fig. 8). The reason was that the critical cells discharge was interrupted already after three hours, while the remaining hundred cells were discharged for eight hours. Already after the one hour of charging, the difference between the critical cell voltages and other cells had additionally risen, reaching even 0.33 V (variation of nearly 15%; the critical cell voltage rose up to 2.55 V). Yet, after the quick voltage rise in the beginning, the weak cell voltages began to decline, in order to reach voltage equalization of all the 102 cells after the five or six hours of charging.

Figure 7. Average battery cell voltages during the charging process of battery B2

However, data obtained after the 24th hour of the charging process points on new variations of the battery cell voltages. In this case voltage variations did not appear only on two weak cells, but on all the battery B2 cells. Noticed process is a consequence of the valve-regulated lead-acid batteries in the floating charge mode. Due to a lack of special modes of boost charge and equalized charge, equalization of the valve-regulated lead-acid battery cell voltages have to be achieved in a float charge mode. Some authors [5] recommend a rectifier, designed for charging of the absorbed-separator valve-regulated lead-acid battery, operate on voltage close to the upper level of the acceptable battery cell voltage (for the AGM SVT 300 battery cell, recommended operation voltage range is 2.25 – 2.3 V). Therefore, for the, e.g., 100 cell battery, appropriate output voltage of the battery charger would be approximately 228 - 229 V. After completion of the deep discharging process, a battery should operate with rectifier for seven days in order to equalize the battery cell voltages [5]. The recommended equalization voltage may be reduced following the elapse of the specified one-week interval, but a battery may permanently remain in this mode of operation. It is important to prevent the excessive voltage rise on individual cells, *i.e.*, to prevent voltage of any cell to be above the maximum recommended operation voltage of 2.3 V when the equalization interval is over [5]. The authors also specify [5] that after 12 hours of a battery charging may be expected increase in the battery cell voltage imbalance, as may be also seen in the case of battery AGM SVT

300 in Fig. 8.

Presented results point on decisive influence of the ambient temperature on a service life and reliability of valve-regulated lead-acid batteries. According to the experience procured during the years of exploitation of the valve-regulated lead-acid batteries, recommendations may be formulated for users of VRLA batteries in industrial uninterruptible power supply systems. If the users already possess a separate room for the accommodation of the storage battery, or may not obtain battery operation with the ambient temperature lower than 25°C, priority has to be on a side of standard, vented lead-acid battery. If the user does not have the possibility to employ staff that should be in charge of the monitoring and maintenance of the battery year around, then as an alternative is imposing purchase of the valve-regulated lead-acid battery. In that case it is necessary to install reliable air-conditioning systems, with the sufficient power to keep the battery temperature below the threshold of 25°C year around. In the case that user is not sure if the battery ambient temperature really may be below the specified limit during the summer months' operation, it is necessary to consider the purchase of the rectifier with the function of the temperature compensation of the output voltage [1, 6].

Figure 8. Variations of minimum and maximum values of the battery cell voltages from the average battery cell voltage during the charging process of the battery B2

Regardless of the temperature conditions, during the operation with the valve-regulated lead-acid battery it is advisable to use the thyristor rectifier with the output filter electrolytic capacitors [7] having the function of the battery availability test [6, 8]. Battery availability test, performed in the relatively short time intervals (30 – 60 minutes), obtains two significant advantages in comparisons with rectifiers lacking this function. The first advantage is a timely detection of the battery circuit failure and activation of the remote failure signaling, alongside the continuous rectifier operation and the power supply of consumers with a direct current even without the proper battery availability. The second significant advantage is manifested in a permanent battery cycling, *i.e.*, hourly bidirectional ions flow through a battery cell. Thus during the ten-second check of the battery availability, rectifier output voltage is being decreased down to 195 V (1.95 V/cell for a battery comprised of hundred cells) [8]. As long as the battery availability test lasts, a battery is discharged if it is correct. If a breach occurred in a battery circuit, a consumer voltage is still kept on acceptable value, 10% lower of the nominal voltage. Brief battery discharge every 30 – 60 minutes, followed by the relatively high current flow through a battery, is expected to assure significantly higher battery performances (this topic was more detailed analyzed in a literature [6, 8, 9]).

Another favorable solution for a high-automation facilities without a crew, or with a few of

occasionally engaged operators, represents the connection of valve-regulated lead-acid batteries on rectifiers with a function of automatic battery circuit test [6]. These rectifiers enable activation of the automatic battery discharge process (*e.g.*, once a week or month). In that case is defined percent of the nominal battery capacity that should be discharged (*e.g.*, 10%, 30 Ah for a 300 Ah battery). In that way could be enabled battery discharging even with the existing consumers, and could last for several hours. This procedure would enable partial battery cycling without a need for the operator's intervention and the consumers disconnection from the battery, leading to the anticipated preservation of the battery's service life and capacity [6].

5. CONCLUSION

In the paper were presented results obtained after six-year exploitation of the valve-regulated lead-acid batteries "Sunlight" AGM SVT 300 in one industrial facility in Serbia. Both batteries operated with identical industrial consumers, yet in different temperature conditions. Prolonged operation of VRLA batteries without air-conditioning, often with very high ambient temperatures in the summer period, may lead to much earlier failure of the individual battery cells than expected by the mere measurement of the ambient temperature. Particularly critical situations are during the operation in a summer months, with atmosphere temperatures exceeding 40°C, simultaneous with the charging process of the discharged battery.

It was also noticed that state recorded immediately after the charging completion may not lead to the correct conclusion on the battery cells correctness. A good illustration is the case of the battery B1 cell no. 74, having a cell voltage increased up to 5.1 V a day after the battery was recharged, whilst the battery current was only 0.3 A. The failure of several battery cells and high voltage of many remaining cells finally led to the conclusion that battery B1 have to be replaced, beside the expiry of only half of the nominal service life.

Operation of the other battery of the same type in well air-conditioned room, after a similar period spent in exploitation (totalling five and a half years), led to the acquisition of the different results. Cells of the battery B2 from the same production batch (100 out of 102 cells) demonstrated high quality and uniformity between the individual cell voltages. During the discharging process of the battery cells from the same batch was depleted 80% of the nominal capacity, leading to the voltage decline to the minimum 1.8 V on only one cell. Yet, from two battery B2 cells that were not from the same batch during the discharging process was depleted only 30% of the nominal capacity, although also these two cells were new ones in a moment of installation, with a minor difference in a production date from the batch with the remaining hundred cells. Finally, it was estimated that battery B2 might remain in exploitation for a long time, with an eventual need to replace two weak cells.

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